

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN PROMOTING DIGITAL ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

Information about the role of information technologies and their use in various areas of the economy is presented.

Key words: *information technology, education, economy, finance, tools, computer, technology.*

INTRODUCTION

It shows that the development of science and digital economy in our country, that is, in the near future, raising the intellectual potential of the population, especially young people, and supporting the field of information and communication technologies will remain one of the priority issues of state policy. Implementation of e-government elements and support of digital economy have a strong place in Uzbekistan's near-term development plan.

In recent years, the importance of advanced technologies and innovation in the development of the economy is increasing. The latest technologies can improve the efficiency of production and business processes. As the latest technologies penetrate

into all new areas and fields of human activity, traditional approaches and ways of working are changing.

The 21st century is the century of "Information technologies". The meaning of this is that information and communication technologies serve as one of the main factors in the life of society and its development. At the current stage of development of our society information and communication technologies play an important role. Information technologies are used in all areas of society including medicine, economy, finance, education, banking system etc. The emergence and spread of information and communication technologies (ICT) has had such an impact on the global economy that a new phenomenon - the digital economy - has appeared.

Under the influence of smart technologies, people's lifestyles began to change, communication between users changed - there was an opportunity to establish communication between people in different geographical regions, fields of activity etc.

This is the prompt growth of information exchange which is the basis of the digital economy. The impact of digital technologies is felt both globally and locally. The importance of advanced technologies and innovations in economic development is expanding. The latest technologies can improve the efficiency of production and business processes. The digital economy is a rapidly growing part of the global economy as a combination of new productions. What is the main goal of the transition to the digital economy? This is to develop the national economy of each country at an optimal level and thereby ensure the material well-being of the people. Using the digital economy, quality service is provided to consumers, buyers and clients, and a number of other opportunities are created. It is useful for ordering lunch or dinner when you have no time to go outside, receiving or transferring money from a distant relative, trans-border business cooperation, online purchase of any item without going to the market, saving time, putting an end to paperwork, accurate calculations, economic and it plays an important role in solving financial problems, in developing management decisions, in the use of economic information technologies, and most importantly, in ensuring transparency.

Today, the importance of digital technologies in society is increasing. Nowadays the diffusion and development of the digital economy have become a serious vital concern for every country. According to experts, in the next 3 years, 22% of jobs in the world will be created with the help of information technologies through the digitization of the economy.

"In the era of digital economy, every member of the information society, including every specialist in the field of economy, must have knowledge and skills related to information technologies. First of all, information technology creates the possibility of working in a corruption-free zone. It is the main enemy of the "hidden economy". Because numbers seal everything and keep it in memory. Numbers provide information quickly when needed. In such conditions, it is impossible to hide information, to sign secret deals, to not provide complete information about an activity," said Minister of Information Technology and Communications Development Shuhrat Sadikov. As a result, funds directed to the economy are spent correctly. In particular, the precise calculation and payment of taxes on time, the transparency of budget distribution, the funds allocated to the social sphere, schools, hospitals, and roads would be able to reach their intended destination. Therefore, it would be a reasonable and fair definition to call digital technologies the shortest way to progress of society.

In conclusion, it can be said that the digital economy cannot be imagined without modern information and communication technologies (ICT) and the global internet. The concepts of "Digital economy" and "Information technologies" are inextricably linked. Digital economy is the newest term in the world economy. Economically developed countries have made a lot of progress in the direction of the digital economy, while other countries are moving forward in this direction. Therefore, all countries that have started to transform their global and regional economies into a digital economy are facing the same problem - in the digital economy in national languages. lack of educational and scientific literature necessary for the training of qualified personnel. World information on the digital economy is increasing significantly

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The spread of information and communication technologies (ICT) affected the world economy in such a way that a new phenomenon - the digital economy - appeared. there was an opportunity to establish communication between people from different geographical regions, fields of activity, etc. It is the growth process of information communication that is the basis of the digital economy.

RESULTS

Digital economy is the management of economic activities, in which the main factor in production and service provision is information in the form of ICT, and with the help of processing a large amount of information and analyzing the result of this processing, various types of production are made. implementation of more effective solutions than the old system in production, service, technologies, devices, storage, product delivery. In other words, providing online services, making electronic payments, trading on the Internet, is an activity associated with the development of digital computer technologies.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, ICT is used in all sectors. If we take the service sector, it is possible to order food online, pay utility bills online, use banking services, take and pay micro and macro loans. there is. This has been creating relief for the way of life of mankind.

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